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Exploring themes of justice, vulnerability and inequality in social innovation processes for the European Green Deal

Part of the Collection: Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes

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Zareen Pervez Bharucha

Global Sustainability Institute
Anglia Ruskin University
UK

*Contact email for corresponding author:
zareen.bharucha@aru.ac.uk

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Executive summary of recommendations

The SHARED GREEN DEAL project involved 24 social experiments to stimulate social innovation for a European Green Deal. These social experiments addressed six topic areas: Clean Energy, Preserving Biodiversity, Circular Economy, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food and Efficient Renovations. Local partners designed social experiments which ran over the course of one year. Each social experiment was given some guidance by the project on relevant vulnerable or marginalised groups to include within their experiment, and many went beyond this 'brief' to ensure a diverse participant pool. Each of these experiments generated a great deal of secondary data that was analysed, within this report, to illuminate the ways in which experiments dealt with issues of marginalisation, vulnerability and inequality. The core focus was on the ways in which innovations ensured procedural justice – that is, the ways in which participants from marginalised and vulnerable groups were included, the quality and depth of their participation and the extent to which they were able to actively shape the outcomes of the experiments.

The recommendations for policy and practice for a just European Green Deal are listed below.

Policy-making on the Green Deal should focus on procedural justice:

Policy making should enshrine an explicit commitment to procedural justice through a well-targeted regulatory and funding environment. Crucially, policy making and practice should explicitly recognise the difference between 'tick box' participation and meaningful engagement, and should put in place assessment or monitoring structures to ensure that marginalised groups are meaningfully involved in the design, planning, monitoring and reflection stages of any innovation activity.

Funding regimes should be tailored to support procedural justice:

Funding regulations for Green Deal initiatives should allow for the active and equal participation of small-scale, community-centred organisations who have 'deep' knowledge of local communities and the specific challenges facing marginalised and vulnerable groups. Funding regimes also need to take into account the need for *long-term* engagement with vulnerable and marginalised communities, and the need to support social engagement and convivial activities to build social and cultural capital. Addressing social and cultural alienation needs to underpin social innovation for a just European Green Deal.

Knowledge-sharing on best-practice:

EU and national bodies should share knowledge on how best to achieve co-production and tackle challenges of inclusion of marginalised and vulnerable groups. 'Best practice' cases, stories of change and a compendium of tools and techniques should be readily available to actors at all scales to facilitate continuous learning.

Support is needed for long-term engagement:

The design of Green Deal initiatives should reflect the need for long-term engagement with local communities. This includes the need for funding to reinvigorate social and cultural capital, to facilitate engagement and to overcome longstanding exclusion. The design of initiatives must include attention to the context-specific and nuanced process of group formation, which is shaped by local cultures and norms. In other words, initiatives should not expect meaningful participation in group processes by people who have been hastily convened. Instead, time and effort must be expended in getting people to work cohesively and convivially. Building social capital must be at the forefront and a prerequisite to any social innovation processes.

Initiatives should focus explicitly and continually on identifying and overcoming barriers to participation:

This should be an ongoing endeavour throughout social innovation processes that seek to be inclusive. Locally-based, community-centred organisations who are well embedded in the local context are very valuable partners in this regard and regulations should be designed to enable their participation.

■ List of Contents

Executive summary of recommendations	3
1. Introduction	5
1.1. Introducing the project	5
1.2. Introducing the report	7
1.3. Introducing Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities.....	8
2. Conceptual and methodological approach	10
2.1. Conceptual lens	10
2.2. Methodology	11
2.2.1. Research questions	11
2.2.2. Analytical framework applied.....	11
2.2.3. Data sources used	13
2.2.4. Analytical approach.....	13
3. Main findings	16
3.1. Overview of the context on inclusion for the six experiment streams	16
3.2. Outcomes from the inclusion of marginalised groups	17
3.3. Barriers to engagement for marginalised groups.....	19
3.4. Navigating social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and designing alternatives ‘from below’	20
3.5. Designing social innovations that take into account complex histories of differentiated access	22
4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance	25
5. Conclusions	27
6. Acknowledgements	28
7. References	29
Appendix	31

■ List of Figures

<i>Figure 1.1. Map of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments</i>	6
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■ List of Tables

<i>Table 1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis</i>	7
<i>Table 2.2a. Main coding categories mapped against research questions</i>	12
<i>Table 2.2b. Summary of when main data sources were collected and whose ‘voice’ was captured</i>	13
<i>Table 2.2c. Full list of main codes for the Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities theme</i>	14
<i>Table 3.1. Inclusion targets set out in SHARED GREEN DEAL Call for Experiments</i>	16
<i>Table A1.1. Social experiments profiles</i>	31
<i>Table A1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis</i>	32

1. Introduction

1.1. Introducing the project

This report presents findings from **Cross-topic comparisons, scaling and synthesis**, building upon previous work packages of the project ‘*Social sciences and Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable Green Deal*’ (SHARED GREEN DEAL). The European Green Deal is a programme of policies aimed at overcoming climate change and environmental degradation by transforming the European Union (EU) into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. The goal of SHARED GREEN DEAL is to stimulate behavioural, social and cultural change across Europe, aligned with the policy priorities of the Green Deal.

SHARED GREEN DEAL provides Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) tools to support the implementation of the Green Deal programme. In the past, SSH research on green transitions has focused on changes to either individuals (‘micro’ phenomena) or systems and collectives (‘macro’ phenomena). In contrast, SHARED GREEN DEAL focuses on ‘middle range’ (‘meso’) changes to bridge these two sets of understandings and priorities (Foulds et al., 2025). Using this innovative ‘meso’ approach, the project links societal actors to foster knowledge sharing, learn from collective experiences, and feed back into ‘macro’ policies and governance.

The SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium brings together 22 leading organisations from across Europe, including universities, research institutions, network organisations and businesses. The project is structured around **six priority Green Deal topics: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Preserving Biodiversity**. Within these six themes, a total of 24 social experiments (Figure 1.1) were delivered across different EU Member States and affiliated countries between April 2023 - June 2024, working with local municipalities and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) (Table A1.1¹). These are called ‘local partners’ and they carried out the social experiments autonomously, with the consortium partners providing initial training and guidance, as well as support whenever needed. Other resources related to the running of and impacts from the social experiments can also be found via www.sharedgreendeal.eu.

1 Further detail about each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments can be found in the project’s Case Study Guides (Kovács et al., 2024).

Figure 1.1. Map of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments (Kovács et al., 2024)

1.2. Introducing the report

This report is based on a secondary analysis of data from the social experiments with the **main objective to identify how Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) priority themes cut across all six experiment streams**. The SSH priority themes are: (1) Gender and Diversity, (2) Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities, (3) Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19, (4) Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions, (5) Geographic Differences and Evolutions across Time.

This report focuses on **Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities**. In it, a reflection is conducted on how the social experiments managed to shape co-creative and inclusive processes which may be supportive of a just transition. Alongside this report, four other reports were published on the respective SSH priority themes.

For the secondary analyses, a variety of data sources, collected within the social experiments, were considered (Table 1.2, below). Tables A1.1 and A1.2 (in the Appendix) provide an overview of the social experiments streams and summarise the data sources in more detail, respectively.

While all data sources were considered during a first round of analysis, not all were equally relevant for all SSH themes. For this report, the main data sources which were found particularly interesting to explore themes related to the theme of Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities were the interviews conducted with participants after each experiment (DS1), the experiment journey and reflective survey completed by each local partner (DS4), and in some cases, the monthly meeting notes (DS3) that allowed a glimpse into the reflections of organizers and academic partners on the unfolding process of stakeholder inclusion and the various challenges and outcomes of this. This report contains insights mainly derived from these sources, though all available data was used to understand the evolution of the experiments.

Table 1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis

Data source (#DS)	Provided by
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants	SGD consortium members (WP4)
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members

1.3. Introducing Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities

This secondary analysis on Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities explores how marginalised and vulnerable social groups are able to actively and meaningfully participate in social innovation processes for a just, green transition in the context of the European Green Deal.

Within this work, ‘justice’ is chiefly addressed in procedural terms. That is, the data is interrogated to understand the ‘how’ of innovation processes, and whether these have led to inclusive and truly co-created outcomes. Procedural justice is concerned with the processes of stakeholder engagement, the ways in which participation is achieved, and the ways in which this participation shapes outcomes (Sovacool et al., 2019). Procedural justice is achieved when all groups – and particularly those most at risk of disadvantage – engage in decision making and are able to really shape outcomes. In other words, participation must go beyond ‘tick box’ exercises, a recognition that has long driven exercises to codify ‘qualities’ of participation or differentiate between different ‘typologies’ of participation (Cornwall, 2008). Indeed, as early as 1969, Arnstein created a notional scale warning against ‘tokenistic’ exercises where simply being represented in an exercise was thought to be sufficient (Arnstein, 1969). Others have followed, notably Pretty (1995), creating a subjective scale with ‘manipulative’ participation at one end, denoting a tick-box exercise where people are only engaged in order to show that an implementing agency is ‘doing the right thing’. At the other end of Pretty’s scale is ‘self-mobilisation’, or the state in which people are able to take charge of change processes.

In other words, it is not simply the presence of diverse stakeholder groups in an exercise that makes it truly inclusive – and potentially thus enabling procedural justice – but the qualities of participation, the extent to which groups have the ability to effect change. Indeed, concerns about whether exercises promote ‘real’ participation remain relevant, decades since Arnstein’s early concerns. Cornwall (2008, p. 269) highlights how ‘participation’ remains “an infinitely malleable concept, [which] can be used to evoke – and to signify – almost anything that involves people.” With a more specific focus on what types of participation may facilitate procedural justice within 378 different energy initiatives across 8 countries, Shejale et al. (2025) distinguish between different forms of engagement which enable different amounts and qualities of participation in collective decision making. They highlight the importance of “deep and inclusive participation” through initiatives which “walk the talk”, by substantively tackling injustice and exclusion (p. 11).

Two important questions for any innovation exercise are thus who is participating, and how are processes designed to allow them do so meaningfully. For the purposes of this report, it is assumed that just Green Deal transitions will need to thus meaningfully engage with groups who are at specific risk of systemic inequalities and vulnerabilities, and enact procedures that ensure they can impact outcomes. As Cornwall (2008, p. 271) reminds us, participation is “ultimately about power and control” and procedural justice is intimately concerned with the processes by which those who are systemically excluded from power and control may be given more influence.

‘Marginalisation’ refers to people’s placement within social and political structures. It denotes limited access to resources and, typically, underrepresentation within decision-making (Kaijser and Kronsell, 2014). The terms marginalization and vulnerability are often used interchangeably (Bueno Patin and Stapper, 2025), and marginalized groups may indeed be vulnerable in the sense of being at greater risk of various harms due to structural exclusion from power, decision-making and resources. As to who should be considered marginalized, there is no single answer to this, and the question itself has received insufficient attention within the literature on just transitions (Wang and Lo, 2021).

Within this report, it is not possible to definitively assess how inclusion has led to particular outcomes for justice or specifically improved conditions for vulnerable groups. Long-term, post-hoc analysis of the 24 social experiments is required for this, which is beyond the scope of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. Nevertheless, there are good reasons to assume that meaningful inclusion helps to ameliorate historic inequalities and reduce marginalisation. ‘Meaningful’ inclusion here denotes processes where marginalised or vulnerable groups truly have a ‘voice’, participate actively and can shape the processes and outcomes of social innovations.

2. Conceptual and methodological approach

This section touches briefly on the conceptual framework which guides this report, and outlines the methods used to analyse the data.

2.1. Conceptual lens

This report uses a ‘just transition’ lens to explore the ways in which social innovations can achieve a just Green Deal.

A just transition discourse is firmly embedded within the policy landscape of the European Green Deal, with attention to the impacts of this transition on marginalized communities. The Green Deal legislation specifically seeks to ‘leave no one behind’. The Just Transition Mechanism is specifically meant to protect the most vulnerable communities and provide support to companies, sectors and indeed, Member States and regions who may be most impacted by transition processes. However, the specific ways in which marginalized communities are portrayed within just transition processes are relatively understudied (Bueno Patin and Stapper, 2025).

Transition scholars have traditionally relied on interpretations of who is vulnerable – such as workers at risk of loss of livelihood, or low-income households. Importantly, these interpretations are often overly-simplified and homogenized (Velicu and Kaika, 2017). Bueno Patin and Stapper (2025), for example, find that the EU’s Territorial Just Transition Plans (TJTTPs) exemplify what may be termed as a ‘simplification’ discourse – or, one in which “people or groups are defined in a generic manner through the broad umbrella of ‘other vulnerable groups’, ‘women’, or ‘people with disabilities’” (p. 15). They go on to discuss how some TJTTPs take a more explicitly intersectional approach that go beyond these ‘single-marker categories’, but nevertheless still portray marginalized communities as passive recipients rather than active agents of change. This matters, because portraying actors as vulnerable in this way elides easily into the assumption that they lack the necessary capacities for meaningful participation in transition processes (Djoudi et al., 2016; Garcia and Tschakert, 2022; Bueno Patin and Stapper, 2025).

It is this question that is chiefly explored within this report – namely, how vulnerable stakeholders can meaningfully participate in the design and running of innovations, what outcomes this has, and what barriers and challenges stand in the way of inclusion.

Within the remainder of this section, the methods used to analyse the data are briefly set out.

2.2. Methodology

2.2.1. Research questions

This report addresses how experiments were designed and run as co-production spaces fostering inclusion and meaningful participation amongst diverse stakeholders, with a particular emphasis on groups which could be considered socially, economically or culturally marginalized.

The research questions specifically addressed are:

1. How does the inclusion of marginalised groups throughout the experiments influence outcomes?
2. What are the barriers to engagement across different social experiment themes for different marginalised groups?
3. How do marginalised groups navigate and negotiate social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and design alternatives ‘from below’?
4. How can social experiments take into account the complex histories of differentiated access to entitlements in their design and implementation?

These questions interrogate the ways in which people participated in processes of co-production, how truly inclusive these processes were and the extent to which these inclusive processes influence experiment outcomes, particularly for marginalized groups.

2.2.2. Analytical framework applied

To an extent, the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments were designed with a certain amount of pre-determined framing of who was considered marginalized. Different experiment streams were designed in order to specifically seek the input of specific groups – such as youth, or the socially isolated, or disabled citizens (see target groups in Table 3.1). However, this report focuses on the extent to which experiments included participants in meaningful co-creation, and the ways in which inclusion shaped outcomes. Below is a summary of the main categories of codes used within this report, as well as how these categories broadly map onto each of the four research questions (Table 2.2a).

Table 2.2a. Main coding categories mapped against research questions

Coding category	Brief description	Research questions
Mode of engagement	Codes related to how experiment organizers designed and ran the experiment activities	RQ3: How do marginalised groups navigate and negotiate social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and design alternatives 'from below'?
Barriers to engagement	Codes related to difficulties with recruitment, retention and effective co-production within the experiment activities.	RQ2: What are the barriers to engagement across different social experiment themes for different marginalized groups? RQ3: How do marginalised groups navigate and negotiate social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and design alternatives 'from below'?
Outcomes from the experiment process	Codes related to outcomes during and immediately following the experiments, including aspects such as group formation and functioning and successful delivery of the experiment aims.	RQ1: How does the inclusion of marginalized groups throughout the experiments influence outcomes? RQ3: How do marginalised groups navigate and negotiate social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and design alternatives 'from below'? RQ4: How can social experiments take into account the complex histories of differentiated access to entitlements in their design and implementation?
Long-term outcomes suggested from participant and organizers testimonies	Post-experiment activities and outcomes suggestive of successful 'just transition' dynamics in action, such as commitment to continuing engagement, or successful intervention or changes.	RQ1: How does the inclusion of marginalized groups throughout the experiments influence outcomes? RQ3: How do marginalised groups navigate and negotiate social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and design alternatives 'from below'? RQ4: How can social experiments take into account the complex histories of differentiated access to entitlements in their design and implementation?
Barriers to outcomes	Codes related to the social, economic, or cultural barriers to social innovation which either shaped the experiment activities or which may constrain the longer-term outcomes desired by participants.	RQ2: What are the barriers to engagement across different social experiment themes for different marginalised groups? RQ3: How do marginalised groups navigate and negotiate social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and design alternatives 'from below'?

2.2.3. Data sources used

This report relies on a rich array of data sources that each helped to build a picture of the ‘qualities’ of people’s engagement in each experiment (Table A1.2 in the Appendix). These sources span different ‘vantage points’ within each experiment, with some pertaining to periods even before the beginning of the experiment journey and others being collected through the one-year period of activity (Table 2.2b). Data is also varied by source: some captures reflections of experiment organizers; other data is composed of a mix of ‘voices’ including both organisers as well as participants, some of whom were members of the general public within the communities where each experiment took place. Table A1.2 (in the Appendix) contains a description of each data source available to the teams undertaking secondary analysis for this task.

It is beyond the scope of this report to comprehensively compare and contrast insights across different data sources; it is expected that this line of analysis will be included in further, forthcoming academic publications.

Table 2.2b. Summary of when main data sources were collected and whose ‘voice’ was captured

Data source	When was the data collected	Whose ‘voice’ was captured
Experiment application	Before the experiments were funded	Local partners who organised the experiment
Monthly meeting notes	Through the running of the experiments	Local partners who organised the experiment
Monthly surveys	Through the running of the experiments	Local partners who organised the experiment
Experiment Journey	After the completion of each experiment	Local partners who organised the experiment
Reflective Survey	After the completion of each experiment	Local partners who organised the experiment
Interviews	After the completion of each experiment	Experiment participants and in a few instances, subcontractors and local partners

As this illustrates, a key aspect to note is that a great deal of the analysed data is thus reliant on the ‘voice’ and perspective of experiment organisers, who have been given a number of opportunities throughout the process to reflect on the experiments as they were running as well as after they were completed.

2.2.4. Analytical approach

Secondary analysis of qualitative data is increasingly common, and is an effective way of maximizing the usefulness of collected data (Hinds et al., 1997; Ruggiano and Perry, 2017). Reports within this collection all use this substantial volume of existing data collected within the course of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project to conduct an in-depth thematic analysis that complements the more topic-focused analysis of the respective experiment streams.

The data sources described above were thematically analysed (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Terry et al., 2017) to identify and organize the most relevant insights from the data, in service of answering the research questions.

The first step was an in-depth familiarization with all the data sources. The aim was to effectively capture the ‘story’ of each experiment, beginning with the application form, and then following the account of the experiment through the monthly meeting notes, ending with the experiment journey and reflective survey. This step was helpful in developing an initial coding framework. The next step was to go through the data sources and code these deductively. The main sources coded this way in Nvivo were the experiment application forms, reflective survey, experiment journey and interview excerpts. Monthly meeting notes and monthly survey questions were not coded within Nvivo, as these were found to be quite variable in depth and relevance to the theme. Instead, these are used as complementary sources to aid understanding of the experiment journey, and relevant quotations from these sources, if any, were made within supplementary notes during the analytical process.

The codes presented below (Table 2.2c) are the result of several rounds of integration, where nested codes were recategorized, merged or deleted. Not all the codes listed below are reported on within the report; instead, the text focuses on selected themes that most strongly illuminate the research questions.

Table 2.2c. Full list of main codes for the Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities theme

Coding category	Codes	Code description
Mode of engagement	Framing	Highlighting efforts to target communications to particular groups
	Navigating emotions	References to the emotional stance brought by participants and how this was navigated during the experiments
	Use of language	References to efforts to pay careful attention to use of language during the experiment
	Group cohesion and care	References to instances of care or group cohesion, denoting formation of bonds between people
	Creative or novel methods	References to the use of creative, playful or novel methods as well as reasons why these methods are well-suited to inclusive and co-creative processes
Barriers to engagement	Lack of expertise	Perceived or actual lack of ‘expertise’ in a subject area or in the methodology being cited as a barrier to recruitment, participation or execution of the experiment
	Rurality or physical isolation	Rurality and physical isolation or lack of transport networks leading to disengagement or difficulties in participating in social innovation
	Social and cultural barriers	References to social or cultural barriers to engagement such as those related to gender, intergenerational dynamics or cultural stance on co-creative practices.
	Barriers specific to particular groups	Statements expressing difficulty with getting certain groups in the room

Coding category	Codes	Code description
Outcomes from the experiment process	Building of social capital	References to groups successfully forming bonds marked by trust and reciprocity
	Experiential learning	References to groups 'learning by doing'
	Increase in participants sense of autonomy or efficacy	Observations that groups took ownership or demonstrated proactive engagement in the issues
	Successful engagement with the topic of the experiment	General positive statements about participants engagement and levels of participation in the experiment
	Participants wanting to learn more	References to participants wanting to learn more about the topic
	Successful creation of close-knit groups	Reflections on how people felt included, closely bonded with group members, or examples of good group dynamics
Long-term outcomes suggested from participant and organizers testimonies	Visions of just or inclusive futures	Groups developing visions of just or inclusive sustainable futures as a result of successful experiment activities
	Overcoming of cultural barriers to engagement in social innovation	Individuals overcoming social and cultural barriers to participation in group or civic processes
	Citizens sharing knowledge with community	Experiment participants sharing examples of spreading learning with friends, family and wider communities, either about the topic or the experiment process
	Specific post-experiment activities	Specific examples of topic-related activities that groups have either done or committed to doing as a result of the experiment
	Capacity building	Participants or organisers finding increased capacity due to increased human or social capital created within the experiments
	Organisational learning on co-production and inclusion	Learning by organizers or other professional stakeholders about the effectiveness of co-production methods
Barriers to outcomes	Barriers to long-term engagement of citizens in civic or group actions	Barriers such as lack of time, busy schedules, or other factors which practically impede participation in civic activities
	Funding	Lack of funding as a barrier to the progress of a social innovation
	Lack of organisational capacity	Barriers pertaining to organizational capacity of experiment organizers or other organisational stakeholders
	Cultural factors	Cultural factors which need to be navigated to ensure people's participation or which are constraining the progress of a social innovation
	Structural factors such as governance or economic architectures	Systems of governance or economic structures which make local social innovations difficult to scale or which constrain its development

3. Main findings

This section elaborates on the ways in which the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments facilitated meaningful inclusion of participants, initiated effective co-production, and the ways in which this inclusion shaped outcomes both within the experiment (i.e., for the running or conduct of the experiment) as well as potentially, afterward. As the data presented will show, efforts to foster meaningful inclusion led to a great deal of positive outcomes both within the experiments as well as further impacts that may potentially benefit marginalised groups. At the same time, these efforts highlighted a number of barriers to inclusion that need to be meaningfully, and continually, engaged with in further work to achieve Green Deal objectives.

3.1. Overview of the context on inclusion for the six experiment streams

By way of background, Table 3.1 summarizes how each experiment stream was framed by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project in terms of social justice challenges, and what kinds of groups local partners were asked to include. These criteria were embedded into the SHARED GREEN DEAL at the project proposal stage, and reflect the specific challenges that were anticipated to particular groups across the different experiments.

Table 3.1. Inclusion targets set out in SHARED GREEN DEAL Call for Experiments

Experiment Stream with a brief description of the main aims	Specific inclusion requirements for experiments across six SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Streams
Biodiversity Preservation <i>To design an adult education programme on biodiversity</i>	To include up to 5 adults who may have experienced social isolation, including due to the Covid-19 pandemic
Clean Energy <i>To use community visioning to build a vision of and capacity for a clean energy future</i>	To include members of the general public of different ages and specifically, young people (18-30) and older generations (+65 years).
Sustainable Food <i>To work with change agents to develop an action agenda for food system transformations</i>	To include young people (18-35), aiming for up to one-third of network members within this age category.
Circular Economy <i>To establish Local Accelerator Hubs (LAHs) to gather and share knowledge on good practices in sustainable and circular models</i>	To include associations for disabled citizens within a local accelerator hub
Sustainable Mobility <i>To set up a mobility lab for smart and sustainable mobility specifically in the context of schools.</i>	To include 30 young people (10-16) in the establishment of an urban mobility lab
Efficient Renovations <i>To form a social network for understanding the importance of renovation.</i>	To include at least 10 households living in energy poverty and aim to engage at least 60% women participants

Most local partners made a concerted effort to target additional marginalized or at-risk groups, based on their reading of the needs within their local context. Indeed, local partners, who did the practical work of organising the experiments, as locally-situated not-for-profit organisations or local/regional government authorities, made implicit or explicit reference to their knowledge of local challenges around vulnerable groups, inequalities and in several cases, highlighted examples of successful work with inclusion.

For example, the Biodiversity Preservation experiment in Greece identified the need to target isolated people via local social services, as well as young people, the elderly and middle-aged people as distinct categories of stakeholders who would all bring something of value to the activities. In Poland, based on their local experience, organizers identified how transitions to clean energy were centrally about gender relations, and so, focused their entire experiment on women participants, going beyond the original call for an experiment that ensured inclusion across different ages. Within the experiment stream on Sustainable Food, local partners in Italy chose to balance age and gender, seeking to involve at least 4 women and 4 young people within the experiment.

I now turn to reflections on how participants – and specifically marginalised or at-risk groups were recruited within the experiment processes. These reflections provide further context on how the work of inclusion was done across the very different terrain of the different experiment streams.

Several experiments have paid particular attention to targeting their communications and designing a targeted recruitment strategy for different groups. Two themes in particular stand out. The first is the great deal of care and sensitivity around the use of language. This involved paying attention to how marginalised groups may receive messages, and using in-depth local knowledge to judge what the most effective messages might be. A good example was provided by the local partners in Jaywick, Essex, setting up the UK Clean Energy experiment. Careful attention was paid to what mattered most to local residents – staying warm in their homes – rather than more abstract topics such as the energy transition. The second noteworthy theme was the use of in-person events and convivial gatherings to bring people together. In the Clean Energy stream for example, local partners set up a social evening serving paella to attract members of the public: “... people came already interested, but also some people just saw a paella and said, “What’s going on there?” [Clean Energy, Spain, Experiment Participant, Man, Community Member, #DS1].

In summary, processes of engagement were carefully crafted to meet the dynamics of particular local contexts. To a large extent, this approach seems to have resulted in fairly successful retention and meaningful participation across the experiments.

3.2. Outcomes from the inclusion of marginalised groups

Experimentation as an approach resists easy recourse to measurement of predetermined outcomes, instead simply serving “to try out new ideas and methods in the context of future uncertainties” (Broto and Bulkeley, 2013, p. 93). Indeed, long-term outcomes from social innovation are recognized to be complex, emerging from interactions between more than one set of actors, and occurring over too long a period to reliably discern linear relationships between actions and impacts (Earl et al., 2001; Antadze and Westley, 2012; Bergmann et al., 2021).

For these reasons, the SHARED GREEN DEAL project did not specifically track outcomes either in general or more specifically, with regard to material changes to the experiences of specific vulnerable groups. Instead, the experiments were viewed as sites in which reflexive, locally-situated and *continually-unfolding* processes of co-produced change could occur. Within this section therefore,

there is no claim of any linear path dependencies between inclusion and particular outcomes. Instead, the analysis picks out reflections from local partners and participants themselves on the ways in which inclusion shaped experiment processes as these unfolded in various ways across very different contexts

The first important theme discussed within this section is outcomes for marginalized or vulnerable people from their inclusion in the experiments. In other words, where inclusion and meaningful participation was acknowledged to have occurred, what did vulnerable or marginalized groups themselves experience as a result?

Testimonies from experiment participants show that social interaction and *convivial*, informal gatherings matter greatly to people's *feeling* of being meaningfully included within a group. Interviewees highlighted how experiment activities had helped them to overcome social isolation. Social isolation spills over into marginalisation from decision-making, and is thus an important 'entry way' into 'just' social innovation. Multi-generational activities were particularly valued, as was the opportunity to meet people with common values and interests.

"The involvement of the students, their participation with other elements, elements of the municipality. I think they felt very important, because they participated with the adults, they felt like members of a group." [Sustainable Mobility, Portugal, Experiment Participant, Woman², Teacher, #DS1]

The second important set of outcomes for participants was the opportunity to engage with relatively close-knit groups over a long period of time. One of the Study Circle 'mentors' within the Greek experiment on Preserving Biodiversity highlighted how:

"...we were a group of people who had different backgrounds, different generations, people who were more knowledgeable than me in this field, people of my age who had the same will to learn, and to be motivated in terms of the environment. I think it was a good mix of people and I think our communication was quite good and very meaningful." [Preserving Biodiversity, Greece, Experiment Participant, Man, Chemical Engineer, #DS1]

This leads to the next theme, which centres on the successful development of social capital – or relations of mutual trust and reciprocity. The development of these relationships was particularly evident within experiments in the Clean Energy stream, amongst women in Poland and socioeconomically vulnerable participants in the UK.

"Fifteen women gave up half of their Saturday, whereas usually, women are bound by a lot of domestic tasks (...) it was a huge success. (...) the women there are very active. Almost immediately, as we introduced ourselves in the first minutes of the workshop, this helped us form such a strong mutual bond. You could feel the chemistry, openness, and great energy between us all." [Clean Energy, Poland, Experiment Participant, Woman, Clerk in Marshall's Office, #DS1]

The second theme relates to learning by marginalised groups participating (sometimes for the first time) in co-production processes, as well as (for other stakeholders) about the particular experiences of marginalised groups and how they relate, uniquely, to the topic at hand. A powerful demonstration of this was found by a student in the 'periscope' activity within the Sustainable Mobility experiments:

"He (the student) had already forgotten how difficult it was for a younger child to live... surrounded by cars, how difficult it was to get around and cross the road and the danger of not being seen by

2 When collecting data on participants' genders, they were asked to self-identify. We report genders using the terms "man", "woman" and "non-binary", in accordance with World Health Organisation guidance on sex and gender terminology. See: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/gender>

drivers. Finally, he proposed that we remove cars from the front of the school and put lighting on the ground at the crosswalks. [Sustainable Mobility, Bulgaria, Experiment Participant, Woman, Official from local Municipality, #DS1]

As one of the participants in the Circular Economy experiment in Cyprus highlighted, “*You think you know something, but when there are many minds from different backgrounds, each one may think something that you didn’t*” [Circular Economy, Cyprus, Experiment Participant, Woman, Chemical Engineer, #DS1].

Within the Sustainable Renovations stream, one of the local partners explained:

“We consider that bringing vulnerable households to the network and giving them space in the discussion was essential, as many times brought the turmoil that vulnerable households have to go through (...) having households, neighbours and professionals listen to the working conditions and workload of public workers helped everyone understand the complexity of the barriers around renovation.” [Efficient Renovations, Spain, local partner, #DS4].

Reflecting on the outcomes of the experiment stream on Sustainable Mobility in Bulgaria, one of the experiment organizers highlighted how they were surprised by the depth and quality of the engagement from the children who participated in the experiment:

“During the project I personally saw the students in a different light, which presented them as thinking children, with many ideas, with suggestions related to their life, how it could be improved. In fact, the children’s ideas turned out to be very good suggestions.” [Sustainable Mobility, Bulgaria, Experiment Participant, Woman, Teacher, #DS1]

In other words, the specific emphasis on inclusion, and sustained focus on the experience of diverse stakeholders, has led to a significant amount of learning. In many cases, this has strengthened an existing commitment to directly tackle the substantial challenges of stakeholder inclusion while ‘doing’ transition work.

3.3. Barriers to engagement for marginalised groups

Within this section, ‘engagement’ encompasses participation by all stakeholder groups involved in each experiment. The focus is then narrowed to narratives from or about marginalised or at-risk groups. Engagement is considered across the time-horizon of the experiment, beginning with successful recruitment to the experiment (or lack thereof), and then continued *meaningful* participation, or the ability to actively and effectively shape the experiments’ process and outcomes.

The first theme relates to general difficulties with engaging members of the general public, within innovation processes that called for citizens to participate. Engagement in activities and meaningful participation across a year-long experiment is time- and energy-intensive. A strong theme in the reflections was the barrier posed by the pace of contemporary life, with citizens’ participation in particular being constrained by commitments around work, family life, caring responsibilities and – more diffusely – by a pervasive disconnection from civic processes in general.

“Well, I get the feeling that it’s difficult to get citizens moving. We are not used to participating in collaborative or community activities. It is true that there is little awareness of the need for people to participate.” [Efficient Renovations, Spain, Experiment Participant, Woman, Social Worker, #DS1]

A related insight was the difficulty of engaging citizens who live in rural locations, and for whom travel is reliant on public transport.

“The size of the Ballyhoura Catchment area has proven to be challenging. There is an extremely poor public transport system in our region and it can be intermittent. This meant that some participants struggled to attend study circles. To counter this challenge, it was decided to move locations of the study circles as much as possible and to hire a bus were feasible.” [Preserving Biodiversity, local partner, Ireland, #DS4]

The second theme pertains to prevailing cultures of knowledge production or civic action, where these impede multi-stakeholder processes or the participation of certain social groups. A key barrier is the influence of ‘expert-led’ cultures of knowledge production. As one local partner explained:

“In Greece, it seems that there is a specific culture that dictates accepting knowledge only from experts of a special field instead of exchanging knowledge and experience with people of our community... it seems that they have not cultivated enough of the cooperative approach which requires their participation in a team with equal... I think people tend to be more open to an expert talking about a field than understanding how they can learn from other people’s experiences.” [Preserving Biodiversity, Greece, local partner, #DS4]

A related insight is the barrier formed by long-standing marginalization and loss of trust. This was exemplified within the experiment on Clean Energy in the UK. This experiment occurred within “a community where people... are very under-served, and this legacy, this history of disadvantage has undermined a lot of trust between the community and the council” [Clean Energy, UK, local partner, Woman, Local Government officer, #DS1]. This resulted in participants from the local council feeling “very nervous about coming into a conversation with the community” [Clean Energy, UK, local partner, Woman, Local Government officer, #DS1].

In other words, barriers to engagement are not restricted to engagement by marginalized or vulnerable populations, but instead, in the context of longstanding vulnerabilities, these may also influence the willingness of ‘expert’ participants or stakeholders with notionally more decision-making power to meaningfully engage in innovation processes.

3.4. Navigating social, cultural, economic or political barriers to social innovation and designing alternatives ‘from below’

This section is focused on how marginalized or vulnerable groups spearheaded the design of social innovations as well as activities and plans beyond the lifetime of the experiments. It first touches on some of the barriers to innovation identified by experiment participants, with a particular focus on those influencing long-term outcomes. The first theme here is broadly related to social structures and cultural paradigms which impede collective or civic action, particularly for certain groups. As several participants highlighted, taking part in co-produced social innovations is time- and energy-intensive and some social groups in particular are likely to find this difficult. Women for example, may be impeded from active participation due to cultural norms on a ‘woman’s place’; children are not typically consulted on policies which affect them. Both groups are expected to spend their time in fairly structured ways. In Poland, for example, one of the experiment participants highlighted the continued influence of social norms shaping women’s participation:

“There are social stereotypes that make women perceive themselves as not good enough to talk about technical, regulatory, or other issues that have historically been more associated with men. This is a challenge we still face regarding women’s participation. We need equitable participation and for women to be seen in all forums more or less equally.” [Clean Energy, Poland, Experiment Participant, Woman, Teacher, #DS1]

Prevailing norms and practices also shape people’s everyday habits, and the ways in which people may see (or fail to see) the need for social innovation. For example, an interviewee from the Sustainable Mobility stream highlighted:

“The main barrier to change the project like this is the fact that in Braga, around 70% of the population use cars for their daily journeys. Even for very short distances, that are compatible with alternative modes. So, therefore, we face unsustainable cultural habits that are deeply rooted in the society and which need laboratories like this to make the change to a more sustainable system.” [Sustainable Mobility, Portugal, Experiment Subcontractor, Woman, Local Municipality officer, DS#1]

The second theme relates to the fact that co-produced social innovations require time, effort and funding, sometimes over an extended period. As several participants highlighted, there was often a strongly-felt need to continue with the experiment activities, but funding was not available for this. Several interviewees highlighted how there is a real danger in convening groups, only to then “disappear, never to be seen again” [Clean Energy, UK, Experiment Participant, Woman, Local Council Housing Advisor, #DS1].

A sustained flow of resources is part of what enables social innovation to come to fruition, or indeed to build momentum for wider transitions. However, this is also contingent on people being able and available to participate over time in order to create ‘deep’ change.

“If the network were to be continued, I think it could be very influential on policy. But I think a more long-term project would have been necessary... network dynamics are always very difficult to set up... I think there is a risk that what has been done will not be of any use. I am sorry to be so frank, but that is the reality. Creating a network that ends in a year has little impact.” [Efficient Renovations, Spain, Experiment Participant, Woman, Energy and People Area Director, #DS1]

The following material turns to reflections on how successful inclusion and co-production has helped participants to try and navigate some of these barriers. In the absence of longitudinal tracking of experiment outcomes or indeed, in the absence of any requirement for sustained engagement beyond the experiment, it is difficult to make any claims that barriers to innovation have been ‘overcome’. Instead, within this section, the report highlights features which are suggestive of experiment participants engaging effectively with these barriers and in doing so, participating in the complex, non-linear and dynamic terrain of transition work. Experiment participants – in particular members of the public from marginalized groups – greatly valued the opportunity to build and share knowledge. As several participants highlighted, in certain contexts, the concept of collective activities such as study circles or other forms of co-production were relatively unknown. Over time, within these contexts, people came to recognize the value of taking ownership of their own learning and building expertise on chosen topics together. Engaging in collective learning has also been personally empowering. In Poland for example, women who had not engaged with the possibility of economic changes brought about by the energy transition, were over the course of the workshops, increasingly aware of the need for building new skills, entering the workforce and participating actively in creatively imagining the future of their town.

“The ladies openly spoke about it during the workshops, saying that they are withdrawn simply because they are the wife of a mine or power plant worker who, as you know, supports the whole

family and earns a lot of money... And at the following workshops, the message was definitely different. The ladies had become so open and thirsty for knowledge... [Clean Energy, Poland, Experiment Participant, Woman, Transition Official, #DS1]

In other words, overcoming social isolation and marginalization allowed people to grapple with some significant social and cultural barriers to designing alternatives ‘from below’. As one of the participants within another Clean Energy experiment put it:

“The best part is being able to get all of this stuff out of my head, just having somewhere where I can go and I can talk to people and they’ll listen and understand what I’m trying to say. I think that’s been the best thing for me is having that opportunity to be able to speak and voice an opinion.” [Clean Energy, UK, Experiment Participant, Man, Business Owner, #DS1]

A second way in which inclusive processes have overcome barriers to innovation is through stimulus to the development of new organisations and group initiatives. In the UK’s Clean Energy experiment, for example, the establishment of a new community energy company was a direct outcome of the inclusive process which was undertaken:

“We’ve gone ahead and set up Jaywick Community Energy now, a new organization ... We’ve got a couple of projects lined up but I don’t know how far I would’ve gone with that if I hadn’t been to the workshops and seen how enthusiastic and how exciting the local populace were for these things and how much they’re crying out for this sort of project.” [Clean Energy, UK, Experiment Participant, Man, Business Owner, #DS1]

Groups – whether formally constituted or informally maintained after the completion of experiments – have allowed people to overcome isolation, empowering further knowledge sharing, dialogue and networking. Experiment participants have also, through their engagement with other stakeholders, been able to join local organisations and even government bodies, in some cases overcoming a long legacy of lack of participation.

A final theme centres on the importance of developing visions for the future, a central element in several of the experiment streams. Visioning exercises, or co-creative methods to collectively imagine alternatives, have helped participants to not just overcome existing barriers to participation, but to proactively shape the design of innovations. As one of the participants within the Italian experiment on Sustainable Food put it: *“... the fact of dreaming together, even if you have different ideas or even different worlds, is not something you do every day”* [Sustainable Food, Italy, Experiment Participant, Woman, Agricultural Worker, #DS1]. In other words, the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments offered a novel chance for people to gather together to develop and share ideas. In Poland, participants within the Clean Energy experiment stream were able to envision new futures together in which *“[there] was no sense of the end of the world, no defeatism, and no catastrophic vision of the end of civilization or prosperity. No. There was a big vision of a new beginning—that this reality is coming to an end—but let’s open up to something new.”* [Clean Energy Poland, Experiment Participant, Woman, Clerk in Local Government office, #DS1]

3.5. Designing social innovations that take into account complex histories of differentiated access

This section summarises reflections on how local partners took into account the specificities of the local socioeconomic and cultural terrains in the design and implementation of SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments.

Local partners who organised SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments were, in many cases, already deeply experienced with the complex terrain of intersecting inequalities that characterised their contexts. Most local partners were very local or regionally-specific third sector organisations or government agencies. As such, this means that the people who facilitated the experiments had excellent local knowledge, in particular of histories of unequal access and factors shaping marginalisation. This knowledge was highlighted within application forms, and comes through in the monthly meeting notes during conversations about how to recruit particular groups of applicants, as well as in reflections on how different groups were engaging within the experiment activities.

It is useful to acknowledge, however, that organizers themselves were partly constrained in the design of their experiments, needing to adhere to a certain minimum brief pre-set by SHARED GREEN DEAL. Application forms detailed this brief, setting out for example the number of events to be run over the course of the year, as well as in some cases, the types of stakeholders who would attend different events (for example, in some cases applicants were asked to design separate events for citizens and other stakeholders, rather than a series of mixed groups). Experiment activities were also not centrally focussed solely on mitigating inequalities – though inclusion and representation of marginalised groups was indeed an important consideration across all the experiments. This means that ‘deep’ knowledge of locally-specific histories had to be applied within the context of a pre-set (though fairly flexible) brief.

The first theme is that local knowledge matters, and that it is best shaped by the people experiencing vulnerabilities or historic inequalities. The design of social innovations can be powerfully shaped by the experiences of those directly experiencing inequalities or systemic marginalisation. As one local partner put it, the best way to really take account of complex histories is “Go and ask; when in doubt, don’t make up ideas from behind a desk. Ask what’s needed, what’s welcome, and what’s discouraged” [Clean Energy, UK, Experiment Participant, Woman, Local Council official, #DS1]. As they went on to highlight, in contexts with entrenched inequalities, the best way for social innovations to really take these into account and deliver effective solutions is to engage directly with the people experiencing them.

“I think we’ve made that mistake so many times, particularly with our really vulnerable communities, like Jaywick, as I say. We’ve come in, there’s always been government presence, and actually it’s around trying to understand what it is genuinely like, the lived experience, and not just... not guessing, but working on our assumptions of what it’s like, actually understanding from them, direct, what it’s like.” [Clean Energy, UK, Experiment Participant, Woman, Local Council official, #DS1]

As the example below shows, even ‘embedded’ organizers can learn something new by hearing directly from local citizens. For an experiment participant within the Sustainable Mobility experiment in Ireland, it was a surprise to learn about the concerns of girls cycling to school, something they had never before considered (and could thus, not account for in the design of any mobility plans):

“... some things were kind of surprising. Like, I wouldn’t have expected that the girls would have been harassed, because, you know, they wear uniforms. And when you see young people on bicycles, like, I can’t imagine what would elicit that kind of inappropriate response. But clearly, it’s an example of things that we don’t know that are happening” [Sustainable Mobility, Ireland, Experiment Participant, Woman, Garden designer, #DS1]

This experience links also to the SSH priority theme on gender and on how questions of vulnerability and justice intersect in this case with gendered learning (see also Aggeli et al., 2025, in this collection).

A second, related theme is the design of social innovations that really allow for effective dialogue between people experiencing inequalities, and decision-makers who design and implement policy. Success in doing this through effective management of group dynamics, has in many cases contributed to professional stakeholders saying they would like to replicate these methods, or apply them to other projects in 'difficult' areas. Complex or challenging histories need to be discussed in forums where unequal power relations do not constrain the discussion, and this was clearly an important theme in experiment organizers' crafting of the experiment activities.

"I've always been a facilitator [for] 20+ years, but sometimes you put people in a room and they don't say what needs to be said because of power relations... the boss is in the room or anything like that." [Clean Energy, UK, Experiment Participant, Man, Consultant, #DS1]

A related theme was that the use of creative and playful methods in particular, is something that they would like to learn more about, to take back to their day-to-day jobs, or indeed specifically to use in the context of working with 'hard to reach' groups. Several interviewees were able to highlight how it was due to the use of these methods which really allowed for marginalized groups to effectively share their experiences.

A related sub-theme was the importance of allowing for deep local histories and entrenched challenges to become visible in the context of a caring and cohesive group. Experiment organizers and participants have reflected on the importance of this across the six experiment streams, and in doing so, highlighted the importance of setting up spaces where people feel safe to discuss or critique the status quo and freely imagine alternatives. In the case of the Clean Energy experiment in Poland, this was powerfully illustrated by the simple decision to move one of the earliest meetings into the kitchen of the venue, which helped the women to feel more comfortable, and to establish a more convivial atmosphere.

4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance

This section summarises the core learnings gained from the data available, and then turns to recommendations for policy makers and practitioners working on social innovation processes within the context of the European Green Deal.

The questions addressed in this report centred on the outcomes resulting from the inclusion of marginalized groups within the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments. The available evidence shows that across the six Green Deal topic areas, the inclusion of marginalized groups within the experiments has had important outcomes for these groups themselves, in addition to actively and helpfully shaping outcomes. As the testimonies captured within this report show, organizers and participants were able to highlight a range of benefits of participation by marginalized groups. Perhaps the most powerful theme here was the profound power of convening groups, with sensitive facilitation, to address social challenges. It is clear that this has been a significantly meaningful experience for participants. This has important justice-related implications that go beyond the specific outcomes of the project. As several interviewees have highlighted, the most valued outcome for certain participants has been a break in their sense of isolation, and a feeling that inertia can be overcome through collective action. In other words, participants feel that they can – sometimes for the first time – engage meaningfully within decision-making spaces and shape outcomes.

The report has also addressed barriers to engagement within the social innovation process for different marginalized groups. There were many insights provided here which are relevant for a broad-based understanding of participation (or difficulties thereof) in social innovation. With regard to marginalized groups in particular, important themes centred on the influence of prevailing cultural norms around knowledge production, as well as the complicated task of building mutual trust and cooperation against a context of marginalization. The next research question focused on the ways in which groups navigate barriers and engage meaningfully in social innovation. A core theme in the responses here is that collective engagement to build and share knowledge matters greatly. Group formation, in other words, allowed people who were traditionally distanced from decision-making processes to engage meaningfully. In a few instances, this has led to the development of formal initiatives and new organisations, indicating a successful initiation of ‘bottom up’ social innovation. The final question related to how social experiments could take into account the complex histories shaping marginalization, and build effective processes to support innovation. The responses here focused heavily on two themes – first, the importance of facilitators with ‘deep’ knowledge of their case study contexts, and second, the importance of creative and playful methods in group facilitation.

The remainder of this section summarises the key recommendations for social innovations aimed at achieving just transitions through the European Green Deal.

The first, overarching recommendation is that the governance landscape within which social innovation processes operate must explicitly support inclusion and procedural justice. The evidence across the SHARED GREEN DEAL dataset highlights how important it is for time, effort and finance

to be available to shape convivial activities which build social and cultural capital. These are the foundation from which inclusive processes emerge, and which shape the meaningful participation of previously-marginalised groups. As others (e.g. Shejale et al. 2025) have pointed out, it is only through meaningful engagement that procedural justice is achieved, and a conducive regulatory framework is essential to this.

Where there is a strongly ‘felt sense’ of meaningful inclusion, it has been largely the outcome of a great deal of time and effort involved in supporting group formation and facilitating social bonds. Sensitive facilitation, targeted communications, and providing relaxed and relatively informal gathering spaces (often including food) is important for rebuilding the lost connections between people which make meaningful civic action possible.

The literature on people’s participation has long highlighted the difference between ‘tick box’ exercises and ‘meaningful’ participation, where people are actively able to shape outcomes and even be accountable for execution, monitoring and course-correction. The next few recommendations focus on the ‘how’ of this meaningful participation. First, inclusive processes are best supported by locally-rooted partners who have ‘deep’ knowledge of the local social and cultural context, and may have existing networks amongst marginalised and vulnerable groups. Second, engaging partners with experience of playful, creative and convivial methods is strongly recommended. The evidence summarised within this report strongly supports the widespread use of these methods *particularly* in contexts characterised by longstanding inequalities and vulnerability. One of the strongest learning points from the available evidence is that these methods help groups to overcome significant barriers to participation, and improve the outcomes from innovation processes. Green Deal policy making can play a key role in expanding the use of these methods, by supporting learning for organisations at all scales, sharing ‘best practice’ case studies and providing funding and support.

5. Conclusions

This report has summarized some of the insights derived from secondary data analysis of available sources from across six experiment streams in the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. The available data sources on each experiment, beginning with application forms from successful experiments, through to reflections from organizers and post-experiment interviews, were analysed thematically in order to answer four interrelated research questions. These questions all centred on the broad theme of exploring how experiments ensured the meaningful engagement of participants, with a particular emphasis on vulnerable or marginalized groups, in order to try and craft 'just' outcomes. Within this section, I briefly reflect on the core conclusions from this analysis as well as set out some reflections on the gaps which further analysis and future publications may address.

The main lessons learned from this analysis centre on the need – already established within literatures on just transitions and co-production, – for engagement which flattens any hierarchies in knowledge production and allows directly-impacted stakeholders to shape innovation processes. The methods used within the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments, in particular creative methods, have allowed citizens from marginalized groups to effectively engage in decision-making, sometimes for the first time in their lives. Testimonies on their experiences, collected through the post-experiment activities, highlight how powerful this experience has been. While the available data does not support any reflection on long-term material outcomes from these innovation processes, what is clear is that the conditions for co-creation and effective engagement have indeed been fostered within the lifetime of the experiments. The central implication for European action on just transitions, and in particular actions undertaken under the Green Deal, is that funding and dedicated support are needed for the careful, time-intensive work of building relationships, fostering group cohesion, and sensitive facilitation that has enabled effective engagement within the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.

In further publications, it would be useful to explore, in detail, the contrasts between perspectives within different sources – some of them in the organizers' voice and others reflecting the experiences of participants (mostly notably, 'everyday' citizens). It would also be useful to compare and contrast how different experiment methods – from study circles to visioning exercises – have crafted different opportunities for participation and indeed, shaped the qualities of participation and engagement by citizens. In other words, this analysis may usefully answer the question of how different forms of co-creative activity have shaped the experience of participants. This may be useful given that different Green Deal topic areas may involve different types of social justice challenges.

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Appendix

Table A1.1. Social experiments profiles

#	Priority area (thematic stream)	Approach	Target group	Place of social experiment	Local partner organisation	Context (rural/urban)*
1	Clean Energy	Community visioning	Policymakers, businesses, local communities	Granada, Spain	Local authority (Diputación de Granada)	mix
				Bełchatów, Poland	NGO (Polish Green Network)	mix
				Jaywick, UK	Local authority (Essex County Council)	rural
				Ærø, Marstal, Denmark	NGO (Fonden Motorfabrikken Marstal and Blue Innovators)	rural
2	Circular Economy	Local accelerator hubs	Local businesses, academics, authorities, and NGOs	Santo Tirso, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Santo Tirso)	urban
				Val-de-Marne, France	NGO (Val de Marne en Transition)	urban
				Nicosia/Limassol/Larnaca, Cyprus	National authority (Cyprus Organization for Standardization)	mix
				Ljubljana, Slovenia	Local authority (Technology Park Ljubljana)	urban
3	Efficient Renovations	Knowledge networks on energy renovation and eco-home-tours	Under-represented and marginalised groups and renovation professionals (40-60% women)	Zaragoza, Spain	NGO (ECODES Zaragoza)	urban
				Nógrád County, Hungary	NGO (Habitat for Humanity Hungary)	rural
				Vilnius, Lithuania	Local authority (Let's Renovate the City Vilnius)	urban
				Louisburgh, Mayo County, Ireland	Regional authority (Mayo County Council Louisburgh)	rural
4	Sustainable Mobility	School mobility labs	Per experiment 30 young people (aged 10-16) and 5 to 10 stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and school administrators	Braga, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Braga)	urban
				Galway, Ireland	NGO (Am Meitheal Rothar Ireland)	urban
				Panevėžys, Lithuania	NGO (ECAT Lithuania)	urban
				Sofia, Bulgaria	NGO (Sofia Development Association Bulgaria)	urban
5	Sustainable Food	Local food Assemblies	Young people aged 18-35 years	Stockholm, Sweden	NGO (REFORMATEN)	urban
				Cella Monte, Italy	NGO (ASFODELO)	rural
				Košice, Slovakia	NGO (Klíma ťa potrebuje)	mix
				Wageningen, Netherlands	NGO (Gemeente Wageningen)	mix
6	Preserving Biodiversity	Study Circles	Diverse group of 10-15 adults per Study Circle (ensure diversity in age, gender, occupation and social vulnerability)	Tolmin, Slovenia	NGO (Posoški razvojni center)	rural
				Amaroussion, Greece	Local authority (Municipality of Amaroussion)	urban
				Kilfinane, Ireland	NGO (Ballyhoura Development CLG)	rural
				Stockholm, Sweden	Local authority (Environment and Health Department of the Municipality of Stockholm)	urban

*Note: Rural/urban is based on [European Commission \(2014\), A harmonised definition of Cities and Rural Areas: The new Degree of Urbanisation.](#)

Table A1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis

Data source (#DS)	Provided by	Comment / Description
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants ¹	SGD consortium members (WP4)	Interviews were conducted by local partners with a variety of participants in social experiments (respecting representative selection criteria), then transcribed and analysed by consortium members. The analysis was guided by specific codes relevant for SSH priority themes - defined ahead - and organized per social experiment stream (Circular Economy, Clean Energy, Efficient Renovation, Sustainable Food, Sustainable Mobility, Preserving Biodiversity), resulting in six codebooks. Per stream, 10 interviews of approx. 30-60 min. were conducted (240 in total).
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners	At the end of each month, local partners filled in a monthly survey about the ongoing experiments that was prepared by the consortium partners, directed already towards SSH priority themes. (288 surveys in total).
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members	Consortium members met with the local partners of each experiment monthly and took note of the developments and progress in the social experiments. For each experiment, the 12th meeting note summarizes all meetings of the past 12 months and reflects on the whole process.
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners	Local partners were given an extensive reflection survey, that included a narrative /qualitative part in which they were asked to reflect and describe the journey of their experiments (24 surveys and 24 experiment journey files (reflections by local partners).
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members	The team of WP 6 - Impact evaluation and RRI integration conducted interviews with respective consortium members of each experiment's stream. (6 interviews in total).
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners	Shared Green Deal's call for application to host social experiments in the six Green Deal priorities areas received 344 applications in which the candidate organizations (NGO's, association, local authorities (municipalities) detailed how they would conduct the experiments and assure qualitative criteria (i.e. inclusive approach) and commit to previous training provided by the project.
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members	Project partners held webinars on each Green Deal priority topic, describing the respective social experiment journeys (https://sharedgreendeal.eu/multimedia/playlist-local-actions-shared-green-deal).

¹ Due to the nature of the qualitative data, openly sharing full datasets would risk compromising participant anonymity. However, anonymised interview transcripts for #DS1 and for each of the six experiment streams are available and can be accessed at the Zenodo platform, community SHARED GREEN DEAL. For **Circular Economy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Circular Economy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387249>; for **Clean Energy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Clean Energy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15274546>; for **Efficient Renovations**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Efficient Renovations [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076033>; for **Sustainable Food**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Food [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387236>; for **Sustainable Mobility**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Mobility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15325897>; for **Preserving Biodiversity**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Preserving Biodiversity [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076035>.

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